

RELIEVING WORK STRESS BY INTEGRATING TRADITIONAL CHINESE MEDICINE AND TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

Fatigue is a complex criterion that may cause to decrease physical performance, motivation, productivity and fatigue. If the work fatigue is not handled properly then it may cause to associated complex problems with decreased work efficiency and competency as well as anxiety enhancement. Symptoms that are often caused by fatigue are stress, headache, muscle pain, concentration problems, anxiety, irritability and easily despair. In traditional Chinese medicine, there are several acupuncture points that are often used to improve one's health. Feng Fu Point is a simple therapeutic method by utilizing cold media placed at the point in the neck to restore the balance of human physiology. This point lies in the body part between the two tendons at the back of neck precisely at the curve between the neck and the head. Based on these problems, researchers have an idea to create a tool that can help to reduce stress and increase productivity. The tool is an integration of the Feng Fu Point method by using a peltier ceramic refrigeration device placed on the cushion of the neck and technology to setting the temperature. The method used to identify the subject matter by using Mental Work Load (BKM) and Cornell Musculoskeletal Discomfort Questionnaires (CMDQ) which resulted in the solution of FUNe Pillow (Feng Fu Neck Pillow) tool. The design of the tool using the method of Quality Function Deployment (QFD) and anthropometric measurement. The anthropometric body dimension used is the Upper Shoulder Width (LBA) and the Back Nose (HBK). In addition FUNe Pillow can also be a solution for increasing the work productivity.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Some of the all employees in Indonesia work as formal workers, such as working in a company or an office. In every year, formal workers in Indonesia have increased. The average working hours is about 7-8 hours per day. The work fatigue may occur due to some external factors such as less ergonomic work environment that includes workplace and work arrangements. These two aspects may cause symptoms of frequent fatigue in the upper body from shoulder to head such as stress, headaches, muscle aches, difficulty concentrating, to the emotional disturbance of workers such as anxiety, irritability, and hopeless. These symptoms will decrease the productivity in workplace and will ultimately affect the occurrence of human error.

FIGURE 1. Number of Formal Workers in Indonesia[1]

Stress is a symptom that often encountered to workers. The impact of stress can be both positive and negative. The positive impact is they are encouraged to complete the works but not that satisfied with the results. However, if stress can not be overcome, it will cause losses of sustainable stress.

FIGURE 2. Factors that affect work stress[2]

In addition, work in office also affect on health if the workplace is not ergonomic, such as the body is too bent, the hand position is not appropriate, the head position is too bowed that can cause Musculoskeletal disorders or MSD. In recent years, MSD becomes the most common health problems for adults. It is a pain that includes nerve abnormalities, tendons, muscles, and ligaments. One of MSDs is pain in the neck can be caused by various types of work the wrong body position that makes the neck in a certain position in the long term. For example, workers who work all day long, work with computers and work using heavy loads. These all can also be caused by repetitive movements of the upper arm and neck, a static load on the muscles of the neck and shoulders, and extreme neck position while working.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Overworking hours may lead to work fatigue both physiologically and psychologically. It may impact on decreased productivity, motivation, even affect on health[3]. According to Charles D Spielberger stress is external demands that affect a person, such as objects in the environment or a stimulus that is objectively harmful[4]. Stress is also commonly interpreted as pressure, tension or unpleasant disturbance that comes from outside of a person. In a

prospective study, Ariens found that workers who worked in static sitting positions > 95% of working time per day were risk factors for neck pain, that can effect productivity. Factors that affect the occurrence of work fatigue are the existence of work monotony; the intensity and duration of disproportionate mental and physical work; work environment, weather and noise factors; mental factors such as responsibility, tension and the existence of conflicts; and the presence of inadequate diseases, pains, and nutrition[5]. According to a scientist named DR. Roger W. Pease Jr, ergonomics is a science application that takes into account the human characteristics that need to be considered in the design and structuring of something that is used, so that between humans and the objects used there will be more convenient and effective interaction[6].

The function of applying ergonomics are to (1) Improve work performance (increase work speed, accuracy, work safety and reduce excessive work energy and reduce fatigue), (2) Reduce wasted time and minimize equipment damage caused by human error, and (3) Improve employee's comfort while working. In traditional Chinese medicine there are several acupuncture points that are often used to improve one's health. Feng Fu Point is a simple therapeutic method by utilizing cold media placed at the points on the neck to restore the balance of human physiology. Based on these problems, researchers have a concept to deal with the problems. They create a neck pillow namely FUNE Pillow (Feng Fu Neck Pillow) by adding point of Feng Fu point massage which is applied peltier ceramic as cooling device at that point. The design of this tool is expected to overcome some symptoms of fatigue physiological and psychological work due to workload that is too high such as reducing the level of stress, fatigue, depression, relieve headaches and other health problems. In addition, FUNE Pillow can also be a useful tool in increasing work productivity.

FIGURE 3. MSD Data of Bank Employees in Punjab, India (Mooma, 2017)

3. PRODUCT DESIGN

Overview

FUNE PILLOW is a neck pillow made from dacron for the inside and latex for the case. This neck pillow has a cooling system that utilizes of peltier ceramic (thermoelectric) as cooling media to substitute ice cooling on Feng Fu Point method. Peltier ceramic has two sides, hot side

and cold side, if the temperature on the hot side getting lower so the cold side will be cooler and can reach temperatures below 0° C.

The cold side works by absorbing heat of summer while the hot side is the part that release the heat . The heat is generated from Dielectric Current (DC) with voltage about 12 volts to 15 volts that supplied from the battery. Peltier cold side ordered with aluminum which is the material of Feng Fu Point. The cool side will deliver cold temperature on aluminum that come indirect contact with the point of the neckline called Feng Fu Point. Using this tool for 10-20 minutes to feel the sensation, initially about 30-40 seconds it will feel cold, but the liquid point will start to warm up.

In Chinese medicine, this point called Feng Fu or wind gate. This point lies in the body part between the two tendons at the back of the neck precisely in the hole or the grooves between the neck and head. The medulla oblongata is structure composed of the lower part of the brainstem, which is responsible for a number of important tasks for human life such as breathing. By pressing, tapping, and massaging the Feng Fu point using a cooling media will stimulate the nerves to connected the primal part of the brain. That is related with a combination of brainstem and cerebellum.

Treatment with Feng Fu point is more effective than acupuncture. The small brain will direct a variety of basic functions, especially in controlling the balancing and coordination the body. Treatment using Feng Fu point also can solve the problem about motoric and motor skills, especially for those related to medulla oblongata function. In addition, insomnia, heart problems, including blood pressure problems can be treated by using Feng Fu point.

Product Specification

TABLE 1. Specification of FUNe Pillow

Components	Materials	Description
The inside parts	Dacron	1 kg
Pillow case	Latex	0,25 m2
Cooler	Peltier ceramic	Freezing to 0 degrees
Battery	Lithium	3000 MAh
Diameter of neck	-	10 cm
Collor	-	magenta

Based on the theme and background problems exist about work fatigue, FUNe Pillow is suitable solution to solve the problem according the theme and it's an innovative tool because FUNe Pillow can reduce work fatigue by using feng fu point method that can rebalancing the body and provide a comfort sense and return spirit or mood due the effects of feng fu point when suppressed with cold media. This feng fu point area can resolve some symptoms such as dealing with headaches and migraines, then creating relaxation effects, produce body power and reduce fatigue, improving respiratory system and cardiovascular system and dealing with psycho-emotional problems, stress, critical fatigue, depression, insomnia.

Detail

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 4. 3D design of FUNe Pillow (a), (b)

Description of figure 4(b) :

1. Pillow
2. Aluminum Alloy
3. Peltier
4. Battery
5. Microcontroller
6. Cover Microcontroller
7. Casse Fune Pillow

Integrating Technology

In setting the temperature of FUNe Pillow, it can be done with applications on the smartphone. So that users don't need difficulty to set the temperature. The application named FUNe Controller. It has been integrated with the pillow so the temperature can be set according the need of the user by installing the application at first.

FIGURE 5. Setting temperature with application on smartphone

FUNe controller which functions as the indicator of the FUNe pillow also can set the temperature of the pillow, the application can show the another information such as real-time and timer. FUNe pillow is connected to the application via Bluetooth, same as if we send using WiFi. FUNe Pillow will send and receive radio waves in the frequency of 79. The use of Bluetooth is due to its low transmitter power resulting from trips to connect to make it faster and safer than wireless networks that operate in longer ranges like Wi-fi. FUNe controller and FUNe Pillow will automatically detect and connect to each other until the eight of them can communicate at the same time. So all the information available in Fune Pillow can be accessed directly using the application.

ERGONOMIC ASPECT

Product Usability

According to ISO 9241-11, usability can be defined as the level of a product that users can use to achieve three specific aim, which are effective, efficient and satisfaction in a context of use. Usability testing on FUNe Pillow was done by interviewing 10 respondents by showing the prototype. Respondents were given 8 questions with answers given in the likert scale, from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The results of usability testing can be seen in the graph below.

FIGURE 6. Result of usability testing

From the graph above, it can be seen that most respondents answered agree and strongly agree on each question, it can be said that the respondent agreed with the statement that FUNe Pillow is usefull, easy to use, easy to learn and satisfying.

User Anthropometric Data

Anthropometry can be interpreted as a science of measurement and the art of applications that define the physical geometry, mass properties and the ability of human body power (Sutalaksana & Widyanti, 2016). In designing a product, measurements using anthropometric dimensions are required to match the usefulness and objectives of the product to be made. FUNe Pillow is designed using two dimensions of anthropometry, the upper shoulder width and the back nose. the details of anthropometric size used are as follows:

TABLE 2. Size Using Anthropometry Dimension

Anthropomethry Dimension	Percentil	Size	Part of Product
Upper shoulder width	50	37,5 cm	Length
Back nose	95	24 cm	Wide side

Based on the table, it can be explained that the length of FUNe Pillow is 37.5 cm and its width is 24 cm. The percentile used for product length is 50th percentile, using the average human size. Width of the product use 95th percentile, taking the largest size of human so that

people who have a large body size can use FUNe Pillow. The thickness of FUNe Pillow is 10 cm.

7. Conclusion

The design of the FUNe Pillow use the concept of ergonomics so it is comfortable to use. In addition, Feng Fu point on the pillow is able to be the best solution to reduce work stress by applying cold energy from ceramic peltier to increase worker productivity. Ease of temperature control is part of the integration of existing technologies of the pillow and the application on smartphones.

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